

Science

MINIMIZATION OF REAL POWER LOSS BY ENHANCED GREAT DELUGE ALGORITHM

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Abstract

This paper presents Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) for solving reactive power problem. Alike other local exploration methods, this Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) also swap general solution (fresh_Config) with most excellent results (most excellent_Config) that have been found by then. This deed prolong until stop conditions is offered. In this algorithm, new solutions are selected from neighbours. Selection strategy is different from other approaches. In order to evaluate validity of the proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm, it has been tested on standard IEEE 118 & practical 191 bus test systems and compared to other standard reported algorithms. Results show that Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) reduces the real power loss and voltage profiles are within the limits.

Keywords: Optimal Reactive Power; Transmission Loss; Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm; Optimization.

Cite This Article: Dr.K.Lenin. (2017). “MINIMIZATION OF REAL POWER LOSS BY ENHANCED GREAT DELUGE ALGORITHM.” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(8), 207-216. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.886353>.

1. Introduction

Optimal reactive power problem is to minimize the real power loss and bus voltage deviation. Various numerical methods like the gradient method [1-2], Newton method [3] and linear programming [4-7] have been adopted to solve the optimal reactive power dispatch problem. Both the gradient and Newton methods have the complexity in managing inequality constraints. If linear programming is applied then the input- output function has to be uttered as a set of linear functions which mostly lead to loss of accuracy. The problem of voltage stability and collapse play a major role in power system planning and operation [8]. Evolutionary algorithms such as genetic algorithm have been already proposed to solve the reactive power flow problem [9-11]. Evolutionary algorithm is a heuristic approach used for minimization problems by utilizing nonlinear and non-differentiable continuous space functions. In [12], Hybrid differential evolution algorithm is proposed to improve the voltage stability index. In [13] Biogeography Based algorithm is projected to solve the reactive power dispatch problem. In [14], a fuzzy based

method is used to solve the optimal reactive power scheduling method. In [15], an improved evolutionary programming is used to solve the optimal reactive power dispatch problem. In [16], the optimal reactive power flow problem is solved by integrating a genetic algorithm with a nonlinear interior point method. In [17], a pattern algorithm is used to solve ac-dc optimal reactive power flow model with the generator capability limits. In [18], F. Capitanescu proposes a two-step approach to evaluate Reactive power reserves with respect to operating constraints and voltage stability. In [19], a programming based approach is used to solve the optimal reactive power dispatch problem. In [20], A. Kargarian et al present a probabilistic algorithm for optimal reactive power provision in hybrid electricity markets with uncertain loads. The Great Deluge algorithm (GD) [21] is a generic algorithm and it alike to the hill-climbing and simulated annealing algorithms. The name comes from the resemblance of a great deluge a person climbing a hill will try to move in any direction that does not get his or her feet wet in the anticipate to find a way up as the water level increases. In this work, we utilize a Great Deluge (GD) algorithm that was introduced by Dueck [21] and applied by Burke *et al.* [22] in different optimization problem to solve the reactive power problem. In proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) model, global and local characters of the algorithms are used in a competent way. In order to evaluate validity of the proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm, it has been tested on standard IEEE 118 & practical 191 bus test systems and compared to other standard reported algorithms. Results show that Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) reduces the real power loss and voltage profiles are within the limits.

2. Problem Formulation

The optimal power flow problem is treated as a general minimization problem with constraints, and can be mathematically written in the following form:

$$\text{Minimize } f(x, u) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{subject to } g(x,u)=0 \quad (2)$$

and

$$h(x, u) \leq 0 \quad (3)$$

where $f(x,u)$ is the objective function. $g(x,u)$ and $h(x,u)$ are respectively the set of equality and inequality constraints. x is the vector of state variables, and u is the vector of control variables.

The state variables are the load buses (PQ buses) voltages, angles, the generator reactive powers and the slack active generator power:

$$x = (P_{g1}, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_N, V_{L1}, \dots, V_{LNL}, Q_{g1}, \dots, Q_{gng})^T \quad (4)$$

The control variables are the generator bus voltages, the shunt capacitors/reactors and the transformers tap-settings:

$$u = (V_g, T, Q_c)^T \quad (5)$$

or

$$u = (V_{g1}, \dots, V_{gng}, T_1, \dots, T_{Nt}, Q_{c1}, \dots, Q_{cnc})^T \quad (6)$$

Where ng , nt and nc are the number of generators, number of tap transformers and the number of shunt compensators respectively.

3. Objective Function

3.1. Active Power Loss

The objective of the reactive power dispatch is to minimize the active power loss in the transmission network, which can be described as follows:

$$F = PL = \sum_{k \in Nbr} g_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (7)$$

or

$$F = PL = \sum_{i \in Ng} P_{gi} - P_d = P_{gslack} + \sum_{i \neq slack}^{Ng} P_{gi} - P_d \quad (8)$$

where g_k : is the conductance of branch between nodes i and j , Nbr : is the total number of transmission lines in power systems. P_d : is the total active power demand, P_{gi} : is the generator active power of unit i , and P_{gslack} : is the generator active power of slack bus.

Voltage Profile Improvement

For minimizing the voltage deviation in PQ buses, the objective function becomes:

$$F = PL + \omega_v \times VD \quad (9)$$

where ω_v : is a weighting factor of voltage deviation.

VD is the voltage deviation given by:

$$VD = \sum_{i=1}^{Npq} |V_i - 1| \quad (10)$$

Equality Constraint

The equality constraint $g(x,u)$ of the ORPD problem is represented by the power balance equation, where the total power generation must cover the total power demand and the power losses:

$$P_G = P_D + P_L \quad (11)$$

This equation is solved by running Newton Raphson load flow method, by calculating the active power of slack bus to determine active power loss.

Inequality Constraints

The inequality constraints $h(x,u)$ reflect the limits on components in the power system as well as the limits created to ensure system security. Upper and lower bounds on the active power of slack bus, and reactive power of generators:

$$P_{gslack}^{min} \leq P_{gslack} \leq P_{gslack}^{max} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_{gi}^{min} \leq Q_{gi} \leq Q_{gi}^{max}, i \in N_g \quad (13)$$

Upper and lower bounds on the bus voltage magnitudes:

$$V_i^{min} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{max}, i \in N \quad (14)$$

Upper and lower bounds on the transformers tap ratios:

$$T_i^{min} \leq T_i \leq T_i^{max}, i \in N_T \quad (15)$$

Upper and lower bounds on the compensators reactive powers:

$$Q_c^{min} \leq Q_c \leq Q_c^{max}, i \in N_c \quad (16)$$

Where N is the total number of buses, N_T is the total number of Transformers; N_c is the total number of shunt reactive compensators.

4. Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm

Great deluge algorithm replaces common solution (*fresh_Config*) with best results (*most excellent_Config*) that have been found by then. This action continues until stop conditions is offered. In this algorithm, novel solutions are chosen from neighbours. In great deluge algorithm these results are satisfactory which their values are equal or better than the value of *Water Level (WL)*. Value of *WL* also increases at a fixed pace in each step. Augment of *WL* persist until value of *WL* equals with the finest result accomplished ever. In this step, the algorithm is repeated several times and if better result is not obtained, it comes to the end. The primary amount of *WL* is equal with the primary results ($f(s)$).

$$\beta = (f(S_o) - \text{est.q}) / N.\text{iters} \quad (17)$$

The Great Deluge algorithm starts with a given *K-Means* partitions i.e. the initial solution is generated by *K-Means* algorithm. Again we list the notations used in this work below:

S_o : initial solution

$f(S_o)$: quality of S_o

$S_{Arrange}$: best solution

$f(S_{Arrange})$: the quality of $S_{Arrange}$

S_{source} : the current solution

$f(S_{source})$: the quality of S_{source}

$S_{working}$: the candidate solution

$f(S_{working})$: the quality of $S_{working}$

level: boundary

est.q: estimated quality of the final solution

N.iters: number of iterations

Iterations: iteration counter

β : decreasing rate *not_improving_length_GD* : maximum number of iterations where there is not improvement in the quality of the solution

In this work, at the beginning of the search, the *level* is set to be initial water level. The water level, *level*, is decreased by β in each of the iteration where β is based on the estimated quality (*est.q*). The pseudo code for the GD to solve clustering problems is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1 shows that, the algorithm starts by initializing the required parameters as in Step-1 by setting the

stopping condition ($N.iters$), estimated quality of the final solution ($est.q$), the initial water level ($level$), decreasing rate (β), maximum number of not improving solutions ($not_improving_length_GD$). Again, note that the initial solution is generated using K -Means (So).

In the improvement phase (Step-2), neighbourhood structures $N1$ and $N2$ are applied to generate candidate solutions (in this case, five candidate solutions are generated), and the best candidate is selected as the candidate solution ($SworKing$) as shown in Step-2.1. In this work there are two cases to be taken into consideration as follows:

Case 1: Better solution

If $f(SworKing)$ is better than $f(SArrange)$, then $SworKing$ is accepted as a current solution ($Ssource \leftarrow SworKing$), and the best solution is updated ($SArrange \leftarrow SworKing$) as shown in Step-2.2. The $level$ will be updated by the value β (i.e. $level = level - \beta$).

Case 2: Worse solution

If $f(SworKing)$ is less than $f(SArrange)$, then the quality of $SworKing$ is compared against the level. If it is less than or equal to the $level$, then $SworKing$ is accepted, and the current solution is updated ($Ssource \leftarrow SworKing$). Otherwise, $SworKing$ will be rejected. The $level$ will be updated by the value β (i.e. $level = level - \beta$). The counter for the non-improving solution is increased by 1. If this counter is equal $not_improving_length_GD$, then the process terminates. Otherwise, the process continues the stopping condition is met (i.e. $Iterations > N.iters$), and return the best solution found $SArrange$. (Step-2). Note that in this work the $est.q$ is set to 0, and $not_improving_length_GD$ is set to 10.

Algorithm of great deluge algorithm

Step-1: Initialization Phase

Determine initial candidate solution So and $f(So)$;
 $SArrange = So$; $f(SArrange) = f(So)$;
 $Ssource = So$; $f(Ssource) = f(So)$;
 Set $N.iters$; (stopping condition)
 Set estimated quality of final solution, $est.q$;
 Set $not_improving_length_GD$; //maximum number of GD not improved
 $level = f(So)$; // initial level
 decreasing rate $\beta = ((f(So) - est.q) / (N.iters))$;
 $Iterations = 0$; $not_improving_counter = 0$;

Step-2: Improvement (Iterative) Phase

repeat (while termination condition is not satisfied)

Step-2.1: Selecting candidate solution $SworKing$

Generate candidate solutions by applying neighbourhood structure ($N1$ and $N2$) and the best solution consider as candidate solution ($SworKing$);

Step-2.2: Accepting Solution

if $f(SworKing) < f(SArrange)$
 $SArrange = SworKing$; $f(SArrange) = f(SworKing)$;
 $Ssource = SworKing$; $f(Ssource) = f(SworKing)$;
 $not_improving_counter = 0$;

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else
if  $f(S_{working}) \leq level$ 
   $S_{source} = S_{working}$ ;
else
  Increase  $not\_improving\_counter$  by one;
  if  $not\_improving\_counter == not\_improving\_length\_GD$ ,
    exit;
  end if
   $level = level - \beta$ ;
end if
  Iterations= Iterations+1;
until Iterations > N.iters (termination condition is met)
Step-3: Termination phase
  Return the best found solution  $S_{Arrange}$ 

```

However, there are three drawbacks in employing the GD algorithm are : (i) in GD the estimated quality (*est.q*) of the final solution is very hard to investigate, as each dataset has its own performance (ii) in GD the acceptance criterion is based on level which is decreased based on the estimated quality that is decreased continuously without control, and (iii) in GD the neighbourhood structure i.e. N1 and N2 are not really effective as it is based at random. Therefore, Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) is proposed to overcome these drawbacks. EDA structure resembles the original structure of the GD algorithm, but the basic difference is in term of updating the *level*. In MGD, we have introduced a list that keeps the previous *level* value at the time when the better solution is obtained (i.e. $S_{Arrange} = S_{working}$). When the maximum number of iteration of no improved GD (*not_improving_length_GD*) is met, then the *level* is updated by a new *level* that is arbitrarily selected.

Enhanced great deluge algorithm for solving reactive power problem

Step-1: Initialization Phase

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Determine initial candidate solution  $S_o$  and  $f(S_o)$ ;
 $S_{Arrange} = S_o$ ;  $f(S_{Arrange}) = f(S_o)$ ;  $S_{source} = S_o$ ;  $f(S_{source}) = f(S_o)$ ;
Set N.iters; (stopping condition)
Set estimated quality of final solution,  $est.q$ ;
Set  $not\_improving\_length\_GD$ ; //maximum number of GD not improved
 $level = f(S_o)$ ; // initial level
Initialize all element in MGD list (LMGD) = Level;
Set Lsize ; CountrMGD =0; // MGD
decreasing rate  $\beta = (f(S_o) - est.q) / (N.iters)$  ;
Iterations=0;  $not\_improving\_counter=0$ ;

```

Step-2: Improvement (Iterative) Phase

repeat (while termination condition is not satisfied)

Step-2.1: Selecting candidate solution $S_{working}$

Generate candidate solutions by applying neighbourhood structure (N1 and N2) and the best solution consider as candidate solution ($S_{working}$);

Step-2.2: Accepting Solution

if $f(S_{working}) < f(S_{Arrange})$

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SArrange = Sworking; f(SArrange)=f(Sworking);
Ssource = Sworking; f(Ssource)=f(Sworking);
not_improving_counter = 0;
CountrMGD = CountrMGD +1; // MGD
IndexMGD = CountrMGD mod Lsize; // MGD
LMGD (IndexMGD) = level; // MGD
else
if  $f(Sworking) \leq level$ 
Ssource = Sworking;
else
Increase not_improving_counter by one;
if not_improving_counter ==not_improving_length_GD,
RN= random number between 1 and Lsize; // MGD
level = LMGD (RN) // MGD
end if
level = level -  $\beta$ ;
end if
Iterations= Iterations+1;
until Iterations > N.iters (termination condition are met)
Step-3: Termination phase
Return the best found solution SArrange.
    
```

5. Simulation Results

At first Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm has been tested in standard IEEE 118-bus test system [23].The system has 54 generator buses, 64 load buses, 186 branches and 9 of them are with the tap setting transformers. The limits of voltage on generator buses are 0.95 - 1.1 per-unit., and on load buses are 0.95 -1.05 per-unit. The limit of transformer rate is 0.9 -1.1, with the changes step of 0.025. The limitations of reactive power source are listed in Table 1, with the change in step of 0.01.

Table 1: Limitation of reactive power sources

BUS	5	34	37	44	45	46	48
QCMAX	0	14	0	10	10	10	15
QCMIN	-40	0	-25	0	0	0	0
BUS	74	79	82	83	105	107	110
QCMAX	12	20	20	10	20	6	6
QCMIN	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The statistical comparison results of 50 trial runs have been list in Table 2 and the results clearly show the better performance of proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm.

Table 2: Comparison results

Active power loss (p.u)	BBO [24]	ILSBBO/strategy1 [24]	ILSBBO/strategy1 [24]	Proposed EDA
Min	128.77	126.98	124.78	116.02
Max	132.64	137.34	132.39	119.24
Average	130.21	130.37	129.22	117.78

Then the Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm has been tested in practical 191 test system and the following results have been obtained. In Practical 191 test bus system – Number of Generators = 20, Number of lines = 200, Number of buses = 191 Number of transmission lines = 55. Table 3 shows the optimal control values of practical 191 test system obtained by Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm. And table 4 shows the results about the value of the real power loss by obtained by Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA).

Table 3: Optimal Control values of Practical 191 utility (Indian) system by EDA method

VG1	1.10		VG 11	0.90
VG 2	0.72		VG 12	1.00
VG 3	1.01		VG 13	1.00
VG 4	1.01		VG 14	0.90
VG 5	1.10		VG 15	1.00
VG 6	1.10		VG 16	1.00
VG 7	1.10		VG 17	0.90
VG 8	1.01		VG 18	1.00
VG 9	1.10		VG 19	1.10
VG 10	1.01		VG 20	1.10

T1	1.00		T21	0.90		T41	0.90
T2	1.00		T22	0.90		T42	0.90
T3	1.00		T23	0.90		T43	0.91
T4	1.10		T24	0.90		T44	0.91
T5	1.00		T25	0.90		T45	0.91
T6	1.00		T26	1.00		T46	0.90
T7	1.00		T27	0.90		T47	0.91
T8	1.01		T28	0.90		T48	1.00
T9	1.00		T29	1.01		T49	0.90
T10	1.00		T30	0.90		T50	0.90
T11	0.90		T31	0.90		T51	0.90
T12	1.00		T32	0.90		T52	0.90
T13	1.01		T33	1.01		T53	1.00
T14	1.01		T34	0.90		T54	0.90
T15	1.01		T35	0.90		T55	0.90
T19	1.02		T39	0.90			
T20	1.01		T40	0.90			

Table 4: Optimum real power loss values obtained for practical 191 utility (Indian) system by EDA method.

Real power Loss (MW)	EDA
Min	144.074
Max	147.142
Average	145.008

6. Conclusion

In this paper a novel approach Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) is successfully solved the optimal reactive power problem. In this proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) model, global and local characters of the algorithms are used in a competent way. In order to evaluate validity of the proposed Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) algorithm, it has been tested on standard IEEE 118 & practical 191 bus test systems and compared to other standard reported algorithms. Results show that Enhanced Great Deluge Algorithm (EDA) reduces the real power loss and voltage profiles are within the limits.

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